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Abstract: *The article presents scientific and methodological provisions, tasks, content and criteria for the effectiveness of long-term sports training.*

Keywords: *long-term sports training, the content of training stages, young athletes, highly qualified athletes, the system of sports competitions.*

Long-term sports training is a single process of competitive and training activities that ensures the continuity of tasks, means, methods, organizational forms of training at the stages: sports and recreation, initial training, training, improving sports skills and higher sports skills. The main criterion for the effectiveness of long-term training is the highest sports result achieved within the optimal age limits for a certain sport. The most important component of sports training is the formation of the personality of an athlete with a high spiritual and moral potential. In the course of long-term sports training, an optimal ratio of various aspects of an athlete's fitness is ensured, strict adherence to gradualness in the process of using training and competitive loads, especially in classes with children, adolescents, boys and girls, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of athletes. The means and methods of pedagogical influence applied during long-term training should not fundamentally change the patterns of age-related psychophysical development of a person.

The goals and objectives of sports training, solved consistently, determine the continuity of its content, as well as the criteria for the success of the training process.

The main content of training and the leading criteria for the preparedness of athletes at the stages of a long-term training process. Each stage of the long-term training of athletes corresponds to certain tasks and criteria for its effectiveness.

The main tasks of sports training

Sports and wellness

- Health promotion;
- mastering the basics of the technique of performing various physical exercises;

- expanding the functional capabilities of the body;
- forming the need for a healthy lifestyle.

Initial training

- Health promotion;
- mastering the basics of the technique of performing various physical exercises and in the chosen sport;
- versatile physical training;
- expanding the functional capabilities of the body;
- participation in mass team competitions;
- harmonious development of personality;
- formation of motivation for classes.

1-2 year of training

- Health promotion;
- in-depth technical training in the chosen sport; general and special physical training; education of strong-willed qualities;
- expansion of functional potential by means of general physical training;
- mastering the volume of educational and training loads by types of training, sports training in the chosen sport; acquisition of competitive experience in the chosen sport.

3-4 year of study

- Mastering the volume of educational and training loads according to the training components provided for by the sports training program;
- increasing and expanding physical and functional potential by means of special physical training;
- improving technical and tactical preparedness in the chosen sport;
- forming emotional and volitional readiness for training and competitive activities;
- expanding the experience of competitive activities.

Sports improvement.

- In-depth individualization of the training process;
- improvement of various aspects of preparedness, in accordance with the requirements of the main competitive exercise;
- increasing the ability to withstand stressful conditions;
- expansion of competitive practice.

The highest sportsmanship

- Maximum realization of motor, mental and intellectual potential in competitive activity

Leading criteria of preparedness

Sports and wellness

- The state of health;
- the level of general physical fitness;
- the naturalness of performing individual basic elements and various holistic movements;
- the basic level of knowledge about a healthy lifestyle, the basics of physical culture and sports, self-control, hygiene, the basics of first aid.

Initial training

- The state of health;
- the level of mastering the basic elements of technique and holistic movements in the chosen sport;
- pronounced dynamics of the increase in individual indicators of general physical fitness.

1-2 year of study

- State of health;
- level of technical readiness in the chosen sport;
- positive dynamics of indicators of physical and functional fitness;
- level of psychological preparedness;
- completed volumes of training loads according to the training program in the chosen sport.

3-4 year of study

- State of health;
- progressive dynamics of the main indicators of general and special physical fitness, functional state, technical and tactical readiness;
- the level of psychological preparedness;
- compliance with the standards and sports categories provided by the training program;
- mastering the volumes of training loads provided by the approximate program of sports training in the chosen sport;
- performance of model indicators of general and special physical fitness;
- fulfillment of the requirements for enrollment in the Olympic reserve schools; - selection for youth national teams in sports

Sports improvement

- The level of sportsmanship;
- performance of model characteristics that determine a high level of special physical, functional, technical and tactical preparedness;
- the level of psychological preparedness;
- fulfillment of classification requirements

The highest sportsmanship

- The level and stability of sports achievements in international competitions

Conclusion: The main methodological provisions of training provide for the continuity of tasks, means and methods of training children, adolescents, young men, juniors and adult athletes, a progressive increase in the volume of general and special physical training, compliance with the principle of gradualness in the process of long-term training of athletes. These provisions should form the basis of program and regulatory documents regulating the work of physical culture and sports organizations that train sports reserves and high-class athletes.

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